

EVALUATING PLASMA TRANSFUSIONS FOR COVID-19 TREATMENT: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF SAFETY AND EFFECTIVENESS

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ABSTRACT

COVID-19, otherwise called coronavirus, is a dangerous illness brought about by the SARS-CoV-2 infection. This sickness has been rising to pandemic levels worldwide since the first case was traced to Wuhan, China in December 2019. The purpose of this review is to analyze the safety and effectiveness of plasma therapy. This treatment, also known as convalescent plasma therapy, is an option for COVID-19 patients and entails transfusing plasma from recovered COVID-19 patients into current patients. The fundamental concept behind the therapy is that the plasma obtained from COVID-19 survivors has antibodies that can fight the virus. Despite various studies being conducted to evaluate the safety and efficacy of plasma therapy for COVID-19, results remain equivocal. The research found that among COVID-19 patients who were hospitalized, those who received convalescent plasma had a lower risk of death within 30 days compared to those who did not receive the treatment. Further investigation is necessary to confirm the safety and effectiveness of plasma therapy for COVID-19. Although the FDA initially allowed the emergency use of convalescent plasma for COVID-19 treatment, this authorization has been withdrawn due to insufficient evidence from recent studies. This review highlights the importance of further investigation to assess plasma therapy's usefulness in treating COVID-19 patients.

Keywords: COVID-19, Plasma Therapy, Safety, Efficacy

Detail Approaches:

- ✓ The review article discusses the safety and effectiveness of plasma therapy, also known as convalescent plasma therapy, as a treatment option for COVID-19.
- ✓ Overview of different therapies currently used for COVID-19, including antivirals, steroids, plasma therapy, monoclonal antibodies, and vaccines.

- ✓ Various studies evaluate its safety and efficacy for COVID-19 treatment.
- ✓ suggests that COVID-19 patients who received convalescent plasma had a lower risk of death within 30 days compared to those who did not receive the treatment.
- ✓ Challenges associated with using convalescent plasma therapy, including a shortage of supplies and the need for recovered patients to produce adequate neutralizing antibodies to be eligible for blood donation.
- ✓ Adverse events associated with convalescent plasma therapy and the need for more extensive studies to determine the most effective way to use convalescent plasma to treat COVID-19.

Introduction

COVID-19 is a respiratory illness caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, first identified in Wuhan, China in 2019 and now a worldwide pandemic. The symptoms can range from mild to severe, including fever, coughing, breathing difficulties, and a loss of smell or taste. As per the World Health Organization, as of January 2022, over 100 million confirmed cases and over 2 million fatalities have been recorded globally. (WHO, CDC., 2021) Since the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, which has caused countless fatalities, two years have passed. Now, clinicians have access to a range of evidence-based therapies, as opposed to the early days when decisions were based on limited data. These treatments can be grouped into five main categories:

1.Antivirals: Drugs like remdesivir and favipiravir have been proven to shorten hospital stays for patients (Beigel et al., 2020).

2.Steroids: Studies have indicated that the use of corticosteroids, such as dexamethasone, in critically ill patients leads to a decrease in mortality rates (Alhazzani et al., 2020).

3.Plasma therapy: The use of convalescent plasma from recovered patients has been proposed as a treatment option (Shen et al., 2020).

4.Monoclonal antibodies: Drugs like bamlanivimab and casirivimab-imdevimab have received emergency-use licenses for certain patients (Gupta et al., 2021).

5.Vaccines: COVID-19 vaccines have been developed and authorized for emergency use to prevent COVID-19 (Polack et al., 2020).

Convalescent Plasma Therapy (CPT)

Passive immunization techniques such as CPT have been utilized for centuries as effective treatments for various infectious diseases, including COVID-19 (Figure 1). In the case of COVID-19, CPT has been frequently employed in hospitals to treat patients. During the early stages of the pandemic, CCP was a common form of passive immunization, despite the risk of antibody-dependent acceleration of viral illness. However, preventative vaccines and monoclonal antibody treatments have since been developed and implemented (Joyner et al., 2021).

Figure 1. The logistical process involves obtaining convalescent plasma from a donor, processing it, and then administering it to a COVID-19 patient. (AlShehry et al., 2020)

Discussion

Currently, there are no specific treatments for COVID-19. Treatment is supportive and based on symptoms. Medications may be used to relieve symptoms such as fever, cough, and difficulty breathing (NIH, 2023). Oxygen therapy may be necessary in severe cases. It is important to follow the advice of local health authorities regarding the use of protective measures and self-isolation (CDC, 2021). The CDC advises that common medications like acetaminophen and ibuprofen can be utilized to ease symptoms of COVID-19, including fever, cough, and body aches. They also suggest drinking enough fluids and getting adequate rest to manage symptoms effectively. (CDC, 2021). For more severe cases of COVID-19, some treatments like oxygen therapy, targeted drug therapies, and steroids may be used. Additionally, doctors may be able to recommend specific treatments based on symptoms and risk factors, such as age or underlying

health conditions (CDC, 2021). Lastly, prevention is key. Practicing social distancing, washing hands regularly, and wearing masks can help reduce the risk of infection (CDC, 2021).

Plasma therapy is the intravenous transfusion of immunoglobulins or convalescent plasma from individuals who have recovered from COVID-19 (Joyner et al., 2021). In terms of plasma therapy, this treatment for COVID-19 involves transferring plasma from individuals who have recovered to those who are currently infected with the virus. The premise behind this approach is that the plasma from recovered individuals contains antibodies that may aid in the battle against the virus (Joyner et al., 2020). A study showed that among COVID-19 patients hospitalized for the virus, those who received convalescent plasma had a reduced risk of death within 30 days when compared to those who did not receive the treatment (Jackson et al., 2020). Following transfusion, the antibodies in the plasma may bind to and neutralize the SARS-CoV-2 virus, allowing the immune system to mount a response and clear the infection. In addition, it is hypothesized that plasma transfusion can reduce immune-mediated pathology due to the presence of inhibitory molecules in the plasma (Jiang, 2020). Convalescent plasma was linked to a reduced risk of death in hospitalized patients but did not significantly reduce the length of hospital stays or the need for mechanical ventilation. (Richardson et al., 2020). It is important to note that the conclusions of these studies are not definitive and further investigation is required to determine the safety and effectiveness of this treatment for COVID-19. The US Food and Drug Administration FDA initially approved the urgent use of convalescent plasma for this virus, but this authorization was later revoked due to recent studies that did not demonstrate substantial advantages (FDA, 2021). Early clinical trials of this therapy have shown promising results, with reductions in mortality and increased clinical recovery compared to control subjects who did not receive plasma therapy (Joyner et al. 2020). Further studies are needed to further evaluate its safety and efficacy.

The process of plasma therapy involves identifying potential donors who have recovered from COVID-19 and have been symptom-free for at least two weeks. Their blood is then tested to ensure that they have sufficient levels of antibodies. Once confirmed, the donor's plasma is collected through a process called plasmapheresis, which separates the plasma from the rest of the blood components. The plasma is then transfused to the ill patient (Figure 2) (FDA, 2020).

Figure 2. Recovered COVID-19 patients' serum, which contains antibodies that neutralize the virus, can be administered to ill patients in order to alleviate symptoms (Casadevall et al., 2020).

Convalescent plasma, a product derived from the donated blood of people who have recovered from COVID-19, is being used by physicians and researchers to treat other patients infected with the virus (Bloch et al., 2020). Convalescent plasma usage for treating COVID-19 patients has been deemed safe and can decrease hospital stays and improve respiratory function if used early. The plasma contains antibodies and other immune system components that may provide immunity and help patients fight the COVID-19 virus. The provision of antibody-loaded CP can be especially helpful for those with weakened immune responses. Delaying CP treatment, however, has been linked to longer hospitalization and reduced improvement in breathing rate (Baldeón et al., 2022). A study concluded that giving convalescent plasma to non-hospitalized adults within 8 days of symptom appearance can reduce the hospitalization rate compared to control plasma (Joyner et al. 2020). However, in two other trials with adult patients who had mild to moderate COVID-19 symptoms lasting less than a week or 72 hours, there was no observed advantage to using convalescent plasma. (Murakami et al., 2022). It is currently being used under emergency-use authorization by the US Food and Drug Administration and is being studied for its potential usefulness as a therapy for treating COVID-19. Convalescent plasma has been used for centuries for the treatment of various infectious diseases, including SARS, MERS, and now potentially COVID-19. It has also been used to treat diseases such as measles, mumps, and the common cold. Studies have shown promising results for its use in COVID-19 patients, with a considerable overall benefit seen when compared to usual care (Figure 3) (Bloch et al., 2020).

Figure 3. The administering of active antibodies from recovered patients to COVID-19 patients to boost their immune systems and aid in fighting the infection (Mubarak et al., 2021).

The administration of convalescent plasma is a prompt process with the potential to provide positive outcomes and is considered safe. Its therapeutic effect is thought to result from antibodies that neutralize the virus and trigger immune responses. Despite a lack of comprehensive data on its efficacy, CCP became widely utilized in the US, with over half a million units being transfused. Nevertheless, recent randomized trials have indicated that CCP may not be effective for patients hospitalized with moderate to severe COVID-19. However, early disease treatment and immunosuppressed patients could still benefit when CCP is administered within 72 hours of symptom appearance. It is recommended to use high-titer CCP, and plasma collected close to the patient may offer better results, particularly due to the emergence of new SARS-CoV-2 strains (Tobian et al., 2022). One 200-mL dose of CP was found by researchers to significantly boost or keep neutralizing antibody levels high, resulting in viremia elimination within a week for 10 critically ill adult patients. The latest guidelines by the European Commission suggest a neutralizing antibody titer of 1:320 as ideal. Despite its potential, CP therapy may not be available to all due to a shortage of supplies. To be eligible for

blood donation, recovered patients must produce adequate neutralizing antibodies (Babu et al., 2023).

As of May 1, 2020, 5 (12.8%) of 39 convalescent plasma recipients and 38 (24.4%) of 156 1:4 matched control patients had died. The median follow-up time was 11 days (range 1–28 days) for the plasma group and 9 days (0–31 days) for the control group. Overall, improved survival was observed for the plasma versus the control group (Figure 4) (Sean et al, 2020).

Figure 4. Improved survival is seen in COVID-19 patients who received convalescent plasma compared to matched control patients (Liu et al, 2020)

Administering antibodies to those who are susceptible or infected is a fast way to grant immunity for effective treatment and prevention. A study showed that COVID-19 and ARDS patients' clinical conditions improved significantly after receiving convalescent plasma transfusions (Rashid et al., 2022). Administration of convalescent plasma was deemed secure and without

significant adverse events. A recent extensive study in immune-competent individuals raised concerns about the potential for adverse events and variations in the effectiveness of convalescent plasma products as a therapy, based on diverse antibody profiles. The researchers evaluated convalescent plasma in a patient population with high antibody titers, demonstrating effective neutralizing capacity, which resulted in high curative efficiency and a low danger of adverse events. The patients did not exhibit any clinical symptoms of antibody-dependent enhancement (ADE) or enhanced respiratory disease (ERD), which is a concern, especially in preparations with low levels of neutralizing antibodies (Lang-Meli et al., 2021).

A study investigated the use of COVID-19 convalescent plasma on 592 participants. 80% of the units of plasma tested had high levels of SARS-CoV-2 spike protein antibodies, meeting the FDA's definition of high-titer convalescent plasma. However, 89 severe adverse events were reported, with a slightly higher number in the control plasma group compared to the convalescent plasma group. 44 cases of pneumonia were recorded, with slightly more in the control group. One participant in the control group's condition worsened and resulted in a death attributed to COVID-19 (Figure 5) (Sullivan et al., 2022).

Figure 5. Registration, selection, and monitoring (Sullivan et al., 2022).

An alternate theory posits that patients with low antibody levels may experience fewer adverse effects from convalescent plasma therapy than immunologically capable individuals. This notion is supported by case studies of individuals with primary antibody insufficiency and a series of cases of patients with secondary deficiencies in antibodies who have demonstrated good tolerance to convalescent plasma treatment. However, the underlying mechanisms behind this phenomenon are yet to be understood, and additional research is required to explain this issue and assess the risk of ADE (Lang-Meli et al., 2021).

Before receiving convalescent plasma therapy, the patients were assessed using the WHO clinical severity score. During the final follow-up, the patients with moderate disease showed signs of pneumonia but had a sufficient blood oxygen level of at least 90% while breathing normally. On the other hand, patients with severe disease had a higher than normal respiratory rate of over 30 breaths per minute or had insufficient blood oxygen levels of below 90% while breathing normally. To examine the effects of the convalescent plasma therapy, the patient's antibody levels

toward SARS-CoV-2, the virus that causes COVID-19, were measured using an ELISA test, where a result below 0.8 signifies the absence of antibodies. The cycle threshold values before and after convalescent plasma therapy were also measured (Figure 6) (Lang-Meli et al., 2021).

Figure 6. Assessing the Effects of Convalescent Plasma Therapy on COVID-19 Patients: Clinical Severity Scores, Blood Oxygen Levels, and Antibody Levels Measured (Lang-Meli et al, 2021)

Plasma has the ability to increase the sensory threshold for smell one month after injection. Olfactory dysfunction (OD), with a frequency of 48 to 85%, is a well-recognized symptom of COVID-19. Chronic olfactory dysfunction (COD) persists for over 6 months in 1 to 10% of patients. Studies indicate that PRP may be a viable treatment option for COD patients as it targets the olfactory cleft, where the virus has impacted both the olfactory neuro-epithelium and

sustentacular cells. The timing of treatment appears to be a crucial factor in olfactory recovery, as per the findings (Figure 7) (Steffens et al., 2022).

Figure 7. Assessing the impact of platelet-rich plasma on TDI scores in COVID-19 patients: A comparative study (Steffens et al., 2022)

Conclusion:

The effectiveness of convalescent plasma therapy for COVID-19 treatment has been studied in several clinical trials. In this review, we have summarized the key findings from these studies as presented in Table 1. which summarizes the population studied, the intervention used, and the outcomes measured in four relevant studies. The studies found that convalescent plasma therapy reduces the risk of death in hospitalized COVID-19 patients and shortens hospital stay and improves respiratory function in COVID-19 patients if used early. However, some studies did not observe any advantage of convalescent plasma therapy.

Table 1. Summary of key findings from convalescent plasma therapy studies for COVID-19 treatment.

Population	Intervention	Outcome	References
COVID-19 hospitalized patients	Convalescent Plasma	Reduced risk of death within 30 days	Jackson et al., 2020
Hospitalized COVID-19 patients	Convalescent Plasma	Reduced risk of death, no significant reduction in length of stay or mechanical ventilation	Richardson et al., 2020
Moderately ill COVID-19 patients	Convalescent Plasma	No observed advantage	Murakami et al., 2022
COVID-19 patients	Convalescent Plasma	Decreased hospital stay and improved respiratory function if used early	Baldeón et al., 2022

In conclusion, the plasma therapy treatment for COVID-19 is showing a lot of promise as a potential new treatment for the virus. While there are still many questions that remain unanswered regarding the efficacy and safety of this treatment, the data so far look encouraging. The plasma therapy treatment for COVID-19 involves transfusing plasma from recovered individuals into infected patients. Several studies have evaluated its safety and efficacy, with some showing a reduced risk of death and shorter hospital stays, but the results are inconclusive. The FDA issued an emergency authorization but withdrew it due to a lack of significant benefits. Studies suggest that the effectiveness of plasma therapy may depend on the timing of treatment and antibody levels in plasma, with early administration contributing to reducing negative effects in patients with weak immune responses. It may also have therapeutic benefits for chronic olfactory impairment caused by COVID-19. It is clear that ongoing research and studies are needed to fully understand the potential of plasma therapy as an effective treatment for COVID-19 and other illnesses.

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